

DEVELOPMENT OF A MODULE FOR EVALUATING THE ACTIVITY OF THE MAKHALLA CHAIRPERSONS BASED ON THE EXPERTS' ASSESSMENT WITH THE ALGORITHMS

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Abstract. *This article deals with the application of machine learning algorithms in the development of a module for evaluating the activity of mahallas based on the employment data of the mahalla. For the issue of classification of machine learning, the construction of a model for the support of Linear Regression, Polynomial Regression and Neural Network algorithms of Machine Learning is mentioned. By using these algorithms, the problem of automatic assessment of mahalla assessment has been solved. Experimental work was carried out on the KNIME Analytics platform. The obtained results are compared for these algorithms and conclusions are presented.*

Keywords: *expert, model, evaluation, linear regression learner, polynomial regression learner, RProp MLP Learner, X-Partitioner, X-Aggregator, error, object.*

Introduction

When analyzing the mahalla data, there is a lot of information that mainly determines the living conditions, material and spiritual condition of the population. The standard of living of the population means the level of providing people with the necessary material and spiritual benefits, the level of satisfying their consumption and needs.[1]

It is possible to consider the standard of living of the population as the level of meeting their material, spiritual and social needs. One of the important indicators in this regard is the employment of the population of the mahalla. Incomplete data on employment is common when data is collected in a cross-sectional area, but if it is discarded during pre-processing of the data, it results in a loss of informative data.[2,3] In the process of building the model, it leads to an increase in errors in the verification of model adequacy.

Experts face a number of difficulties in assessing the activity of the mahalla chairman, especially based on the existing indicators of employment, due to the large number of mahallas. To upload the evaluation process to the system, building a model for evaluating the mahallas according to the employment indicator will allow mahalla chairmen to compare their performance with other mahallas. Classification methods and algorithms of machine learning based on available data help to solve the problem.[4,5]

Setting the question. When solving the problem of classification into classes, the use of methods such as properly distributed neural network, Logistic regression, Naive Bayes, Base vectors, Random forest, and nearest neighbor gives good results. Many classification algorithms have been developed based on these methods. Each of them works well on different types of

datasets. Therefore, it is important to determine which classification method is effective in solving the classification problem for the data set we have chosen. As an efficiency indicator, it is necessary to consider not only the classification error rate, but also the time taken to execute the algorithm as an efficiency indicator. Therefore, in solving the problem of classification in this article, the main issue is to choose a teaching method that minimizes both the error in classification and the time spent on the teaching process for the given set of data.

Therefore, it is advisable to use a more complicated, but more reliable testing method. One such method is the K-Fold Cross-Validation testing method for assessing model reliability. In this way, we can describe the testing process as follows. The main aspect of this method is that all the subjects participate in both the teaching process and the testing process. (See Figure 1).

Figure 1. Splitting the running sample into subsets using the K-Fold Cross-Validation testing method.

In the K-Fold Cross-Validation testing method, the set of running samples is divided into k subsets. The model is then run and tested k times. Each time it is run, the i -th set is used only for testing, and the rest are used for running. Accordingly, the error is calculated for each test, and the average error is determined by the following formula.

$$E_o = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{i=1}^k E_i$$

Using data on employment of residents of mahallas in Khorezm region (Table 1), a data set is developed, looking at each mahalla as an object.[10,11]

Table 1.

Demographic indicators and employment indicators in the areas of the regions and expert assessment

Makhallas	Population	The number of families	Number of pensioners	The number of people under the age of 18	Number of people engaged in child care	Number of permanently employed	People engaged in businesses	Number of unemployed	Expert assessment

Uslar	2371	649	194	726	182	486	149	189	86
Yuksa lish	3314	667	314	981	248	617	164	208	71
Namu na	2857	797	356	1208	245	64	129	138	75
Gulzo r	4012	915	283	1374	150	423	917	270	72
Bogzo r	3723	745	389	1344	205	0	144	243	76
Uzbek istan	4861	1203	124	1754	386	811	202	215	68
Navba khor	6347	1945	389	2443	432	281	328	234	65

The regression problem, which is a part of the classification problem, is solved for the generated running sample.

Regression is one of the methods of intellectual analysis of data and is a set of statistical processes for evaluating the relationship between variables related to an object or process. Linear regression analysis. Regression analysis is widely used mainly for prediction and forecasting, and now the use of this method is compatible with the field of machine learning [8]. In linear regression, the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable is usually done through a line that represents the relationship between the two variables. The corresponding line is called the regression line and $y = a * x + b$ is represented by a linear equation. if we have more than one independent variable, then we consider a multiple linear regression model if we take the following model:
 $y = b_0 + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + \dots + b_nx_n$

- y- is the response to the values, that is, it means the result predicted by the model;
- b_0 the intercept, which is the value of x for which y is all 0;
- the first sign $b_1 x_1$ coefficient1;
- another characteristic is the $b_n x$ coefficient;
- $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ are independent variables of the model.

Basically, an equation explains the relationship between a constant dependent variable (y) and two or more independent variables ($x_1, x_2, x_3 \dots$). In polynomial regression, the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable is usually represented by a Polynomial, which represents the relationship between the two variables.

File Reader: Data is downloaded through this component. The downloaded data will look like this.

Row ID	Col0	Col1	Col2	Col3	Col4	Col5	Col6	Col7	Col8	Col9
Row0	2371	649	194	726	182	486	149	312	189	86
Row1	3314	667	314	981	248	617	164	421	208	71
Row2	2857	797	356	1208	245	64	129	83	138	75
Row3	4012	915	283	1374	150	423	917	489	270	72
Row4	3723	745	389	1344	205	0	144	147	243	76
Row5	4861	1203	124	1754	386	811	202	316	215	68
Row6	6347	1945	389	2443	432	281	328	285	234	65
Row7	4114	1039	397	1402	29	786	365	342	136	73
Row8	3386	935	283	1010	115	481	414	280	217	86
Row9	3305	925	334	926	23	781	298	345	145	86
Row10	3468	874	523	1285	29	102	124	275	255	87

Figure 3. Downloading the data formed on the basis of the data of the mahallas.

Normalizer: Through this component, the data we have is normalized (minmax is transferred to the [0..1] range by normalization. This process is necessary to give the same weight to all symbols)

Row ID	D Col0	D Col1	D Col2	D Col3	D Col4	D Col5	D Col6	D Col7	D Col8	D Col9
Row0	0.133	0.182	0.153	0.164	0.392	0.295	0.037	0.256	0.213	0.745
Row1	0.266	0.191	0.268	0.26	0.552	0.374	0.043	0.345	0.234	0.426
Row2	0.201	0.255	0.309	0.345	0.545	0.039	0.028	0.068	0.156	0.511
Row3	0.364	0.314	0.238	0.407	0.314	0.256	0.372	0.4	0.304	0.447
Row4	0.323	0.229	0.34	0.396	0.448	0	0.035	0.12	0.274	0.532
Row5	0.483	0.456	0.086	0.55	0.888	0.492	0.06	0.259	0.242	0.362
Row6	0.693	0.824	0.34	0.808	1	0.17	0.115	0.233	0.264	0.298
Row7	0.378	0.375	0.348	0.418	0.019	0.476	0.131	0.28	0.153	0.468
Row8	0.276	0.323	0.238	0.271	0.229	0.292	0.152	0.229	0.245	0.745
Row9	0.264	0.318	0.288	0.239	0.005	0.473	0.102	0.283	0.163	0.745
Row10	0.287	0.293	0.469	0.374	0.019	0.062	0.026	0.225	0.287	0.766

Figure 4. View of the data set after normalization.

X-Partitioner and X-Aggregator: K-Fold Cross-Validation running and testing samples forming components, divides the running samples into k parts and organizes the running process k times

$$.Y_1 = -0,5823 * x_1 - 0,347 * x_2 - 0,2316 * x_3 - 0,4682 * x_4 - 0,4759 * x_5 - 0,3101 * x_6 + 0,00048 * x_7 - 0,0909 * x_8 + 0,1683 * x_1^2 - 0,3748 * x_2^2 + 0,198 * x_3^2 + 0,2268 * x_4^2 + 0,287 * x_5^2 + 0,2266 * x_6^2 - 0,161 * x_7^2 + 0,059 * x_8^2$$

R-Squared: 0,7163

Adjusted R-Squared: 0,6964

Linear Regression Learner: Through this component, we check the adequacy of the model built using Regression learner. This is done by giving the tested sample to the regression predictor. After testing, the Line Chart component is used to visualize how different the results are from the real situation, and the error is as follows.[12]

$$Y_1 = -0,2315 * x_1 - 0,0889 * x_2 - 0,2799 * x_3 - 0,3407 * x_4 - 0,2359 * x_5 - 0,0879 * x_6 - 0,173 * x_7 - 0,0731 * x_8;$$

R-Squared: 0,6799

Adjusted R-Squared: 0,669

Row ID	S Variable	D Coeff.	D Std. Err.	D t-value	D ▲ P> t
Row10	Intercept	1.047	0.027	38.233	0
Row3	Col2	-0.28	0.06	-4.645	0
Row5	Col4	-0.236	0.053	-4.464	0
Row4	Col3	-0.341	0.095	-3.579	0
Row7	Col6	-0.173	0.067	-2.573	0.011
Row1	Col0	-0.232	0.141	-1.636	0.103
Row6	Col5	-0.088	0.056	-1.58	0.115
Row8	Col7	-0.073	0.083	-0.879	0.38
Row2	Col1	-0.089	0.112	-0.792	0.429
Row9	Col8	-0.058	0.077	-0.754	0.452

Figure 5. The error was detected using the Linear Regression Learner method.

Polynomial Regression Learner: we can build a regression database and get the following nonlinear information.

R-Squared: 0,7163

Adjusted R-Squared: 0,6964

Figure 6. Using the Polynomial Regression Learner method, the database and the error were identified.

Through RProp MLP Learner: we build the regression database and get the following graph.

Figure 7. Initial and final values are shown in the RProp MLP Learner method.

Table 2.

Experts' assessment			
№	Linear Regression Learner	Polynomial Regression Learner	RProp MLP Learner
1	0.024	0.021	0.009
2	0.019	0.014	0.008
3	0.023	0.016	0.024

Conclusion. In conclusion, it was found that the model of machine learning using linear, polynomial regression and multi-layer neural network methods for evaluating the activity of the chairman of the neighborhood based on neighborhood data is more effective than the model built using Neyorn's network method than linear and polynomial regression methods.

REFERENCES

1. Development of algorithms and software products for personality recognition based on speech signal processing S Ismoilov, O Masharipov, M Ibragimov, AIP Conference Proceedings, 2022
2. Ibragimov Mukhiddin Fakhraddin ugli EURASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES Volume 2 Issue 14, December 2022 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7485196>
3. Ijro Hokimiyati Organlarda Qaror Qabul Qilishning Intelektual Algoritmlarini Ishlab Chiqish Va Uni Tadbiiq Qilish I.M. Fahraddin o'g'li - Kompyuter texnologiyalari, 2022
4. Madeling using polynomial regression algorithms of machine learning on mahalla data O.K.Xujaev M.F.Ibragimov
5. THE IMPORTANCE OF MONITORING IN THE MANAGENT OF SOCIO-ECONOMIO PROCESSES IN SELF- GOVERNMENT BODIES M.F.Ibragimov, O.K.Xujaev
6. К вопросу Оценки Компетентности Подготовки Будущих Бакалавров «Программный Инжиниринг» В Слабо Формализованных Условиях Ф Юсупов, О Казаков, М Ибрагимов.
7. Tomas Loster. KLAŠTER TAHLILIDA KLAŠTERLARNING OPTAL SONINI ANIQLASH. 10-Xalqaro statistika va iqtisodiyot kunlari. Konferensiya materiallari. 2016 yil 8–10 sentyabr; Praga, Chexiya. pp. 1078–1090.
8. X. Rahimboev., M. Ismoilov. "Boshqaruv ob'ekti va uning tarkibiy qismlarining holatini parametrik baholash uchun modelni yaratish". Acta Turin Polytech. Univ. Toshkent, jild. 10, yo'q. 2, bet. 19–33, 2020. <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/actatpu/vol10/iss2/11>.
9. Raximboyev XJ "Mashinada o'qitishdan foydalangan holda o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlarida qarorlar qabul qilishni qo'llab-quvvatlash algoritmini ishlab chiqish" Ilmiy- texnika jurnali, FerPI, 2020 yil, V.24, №6. 23-30-betlar. <https://uzjournals.edu.uz/ferpi/vol24/iss6/4>
10. Dubina, I. N. Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy jarayonlarni matematik modellashtirish asoslari: bakalavriat va magistratura talabalari uchun darslik va amaliy mashg'ulot / I. N. Dubina. - Moskva: Yurayt nashriyoti, 2019. - 349 b.
11. A. A. Barseghyan, M. S. Kupriyanov, I. I. Xolod, M. D. Tess va S. I. Elizarov. Ma'lumotlar va jarayonlarni tahlil qilish: darslik. nafaqa. - 3-nashr, qayta ko'rib chiqilgan. va qo'shimcha - Sankt-Peterburg: BHV-Peterburg, 2009. - 512 p.: kasal. + CD-ROM.
12. Prokopenko, N. Yu. Qarorlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimlari: darslik / N. Yu. Prokopenko; Nijniy Novgorod davlat arxitektura va qurilish universiteti. - Nijniy Novgorod: Nijniy Novgorod davlat arxitektura va qurilish universiteti, 2017 yil.
13. Kornikov V.V., Seregin I.A., Xovanov N.V. Og'irlik koeffitsientlari haqida raqamli bo'lmagan, noto'g'ri va to'liq bo'lmagan ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash uchun Bayes modeli // <http://inftech.webservis.ru/it/conference/scm/2000/session3/kornikov.htm>
14. <https://www.knime.com/knime-analytics-platform>
15. Sahami M. Learning limited dependence Bayesian classifiers // Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining. – Portland, Ore, USA, 1996. – P. 335–338
16. Friedman N. Learning belief networks in the presence of missing values and hidden variables // Proceedings of the 14th International Conference on Machine Learning. – 1997. – P. 125–133.